

Supplementary Material 2

Indices and relevant questions

INDEX	Questions considered in the index
Knowledge Index (KI)	21. Normally, how long does an egg survive after ovulation in the female body? 22. Normally, how long does sperm survive in the female body? 23. Normally, when does ovulation of an egg occur in a 30-day cycle? 24. Which contraceptive methods do you know of? Name a few. 26. Which sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) are you familiar with? Name a few
Education Index (EI)	7a. [Sex education training in high school] 7b. [Biology I course at Deree] 7c. [Biology II course at Deree] 7d. [Other university courses where you were exposed to sex education, human reproduction, STDs and contraception]
Perception Index (PI)	8. Please check the appropriate answer for each of the following statements 8a [I am well informed in the matters of sex] 8c [I am well informed about contraceptive methods.] 8d [I know how Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) are transmitted.] 8e [I understand the difference among the various microorganisms causing STDs] 8f [I know about the different types of treatment of STDs] 8g [I know how to practice safe sex] NOTE: b not included in the index because it referred to the respondent's partner
Behavior Index (BI)	15. If you have experienced or are thinking of having sex: 15a. [...You use/will use a condom each time] 15b. [...You only have/will only have sex with your sexual partner] 15c. [...You avoid anal sex] 15d. [...You avoid oral sex] 15e. [...You avoid oral sex when you have a mouth ulcer or wound on your genitals.] 15g. [...You will use two condoms at the same time] 15h. [...You will request that your sexual partner will take a blood test beforehand] 15i. [...You will take a blood test yourself in advance] 15j. [...You do not have sex without contraception]